

COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS OF LEVENBERG-MARQUARDT METHOD IN NONLINEAR LEAST SQUARES PROBLEMS

Vasco Ricardo¹, Celestino Coelho¹, Ana C. Conceição^{1,2} and Jéssica C. Pires³

1: Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia, Universidade do Algarve
Campus de Gambelas, 8005 - 139 Faro, Portugal

2: Center for Research & Development in Mathematics and Applications
Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810 - 193 Aveiro, Portugal

3: Faculdade de Economia, Universidade do Algarve
Campus de Gambelas, 8005 - 139 Faro, Portugal

e-mail: {a79789, ccoelho, aconcei, jccpires}@ualg.pt

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Abstract. *The Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) method is a widely used optimization algorithm for solving nonlinear least squares problems, particularly in parameter estimation and curve fitting. This work presents a comprehensive study of the method, analyzing its theoretical foundations, convergence properties, and computational performance. The LM method is an iterative algorithm that combines the advantages of gradient descent for global convergence and the Gauss-Newton method (GN) for fast local convergence. The algorithm introduces a damping parameter that dynamically adjusts between the two methods, enhancing stability and efficiency when solving ill-conditioned or highly nonlinear problems.*

This work explores the role of the damping parameter in the convergence process, the sensitivity to initial parameter guesses, and the numerical stability of the algorithm. The implementation of the LM method is carried out in Python, with comparative analysis against the `nls()` function from R software, which uses GN method. Practical examples are used to illustrate the algorithm's performance. The results highlight the advantages of the LM method in terms of convergence speed and robustness, especially in cases where traditional methods like GN method struggle to converge. This analysis contributes to a better understanding of the LM method's application in nonlinear regression problems and its suitability for different problem scenarios.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Complex phenomena that occur in many scientific areas are often studied using mathematical models. These models can be divided into two groups, linear and nonlinear. Linear models are widely used, and their mathematical foundations are easier to understand. The exponential model is found among the nonlinear models, and it is one of the most applied models in scientific studies. The range of scientific applications of this model ranges from health sciences, when exploring the growth of COVID-19 cases, [Kasilingam et al., 2021], to biology, modeling the growth of bacteria count data, [Rumpf, 2021], and economics, to study firm capital structure, [Ramalho et al., 2018], ...

To estimate the unknown parameters of a mathematical model, such as the exponential model, it is common to fit the parameterized model to the collected data. This procedure consists in taking the sum of squared errors between the measured and fitted values as an objective function and applying numerical optimization algorithms ([Björck, 1996]; [Nocedal and Wright, 2006]) to obtain approximations for the unknown parameters of the model, such that the objective function is minimized and the estimates of the parameters are as close as possible to the true values.

The LM method is a widely used optimization algorithm for solving nonlinear least-squares problems. It is particularly effective in scenarios where models need to be fitted to empirical data, such as parameter estimation in exponential models. The method is an adaptive approach that combines the advantages of both the GN method and gradient descent, making it well-suited for problems where the Jacobian matrix is ill-conditioned or nearly singular, leading to numerical instability. Regularization techniques, such as the LM method, help mitigate these issues by introducing adaptive damping parameters to balance between rapid convergence and numerical robustness.

In this work, we explore the application of these two methods, GN and LM, using implemented code in Python and the `nls()` function available in statistical software. One of the main purposes of this work is to understand how these methods behave in terms of convergence when using initial approximations far from the real estimates of the parameters of the model.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 covers the theoretical analysis related to nonlinear least-squares regression problems and the derivation of numerical algorithms to solve this kind of problems; Some of the numerical results obtained are presented in Section 3; Section 4 is used to draw some final remarks.

2 THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

2.1 Nonlinear least-squares problem

The main goal in a least-squares problem is to minimize the Euclidean norm of the residual. The residual function r depends on the n parameters to estimate and has m components, generally m is much larger than n .

If the model to fit is linear on the dependent variable, we will get a linear least-squares

problem whose solution can be easily obtained using the normal equations or the QR decomposition.

The nonlinear least-squares problem arises most commonly from data-fitting applications, when we attempt to fit the data (x_i, y_i) , $i = 1, \dots, m$, with a mathematical model $\phi(\beta; x)$ that is nonlinear in β . In such cases, each component of the residual function is given by

$$r_i(\beta) = \phi(\beta; x_i) - y_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, m, \quad (1)$$

and the nonlinear least-squares problem consists of choosing β so that the fit is as close as possible in the sense that the sum of the squares of the residuals is minimized, which is equivalent to minimize the objective function:

$$f(\beta; x, y) \equiv f(\beta) = \frac{1}{2} \|r(\beta)\|^2 = \frac{1}{2} r(\beta)^T r(\beta). \quad (2)$$

The sum-of-squares measure for data fitting is justified by statistical considerations and the problem can be stated as follows:

$$\min_{\beta \in \mathbb{R}^n} f(\beta) = \min_{\beta \in \mathbb{R}^n} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m (\phi(\beta, x_i) - y_i)^2. \quad (3)$$

Taking the first derivative of the objective function presented in (2) we get:

$$\nabla f = \sum_{i=1}^m r_i \cdot \nabla r_i = J^T r \quad (4)$$

where $J \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is the Jacobian matrix with $J_{ij} = J(\beta)_{ij} = \frac{\partial r_i}{\partial \beta_j}(\beta)$.

Analogously, the second derivative is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2 f &= \sum_{i=1}^m (\nabla r_i \cdot \nabla r_i^T + r_i \cdot \nabla^2 r_i) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^m (\nabla r_i \cdot \nabla r_i^T) + \sum_{i=1}^m (r_i \cdot \nabla^2 r_i) \\ &= J^T J + S, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where S denotes the second order terms in $\nabla^2 f$. Therefore, taking the second order approximation from Taylor series expansion around β_c we get:

$$\begin{aligned} f(\beta_c + h) &\approx f(\beta_c) + \nabla f(\beta_c)^T h + \frac{1}{2} h^T \nabla^2 f(\beta_c) h \\ &\approx \frac{1}{2} r(\beta_c)^T r(\beta_c) + r(\beta_c)^T J(\beta_c) h + \frac{1}{2} h^T \left(J(\beta_c)^T J(\beta_c) + S(\beta_c) \right) h \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $h = \beta - \beta_c$. Applying the idea that underlies Newton's method derivation we get the iterative scheme:

$$\beta^{(k+1)} = \beta^{(k)} - (J_k^T J_k + S_k)^{-1} J_k^T r^{(k)}. \quad (7)$$

where $J_k = J(\beta^{(k)})$, $S_k = S(\beta^{(k)})$ and $r^{(k)} = r(\beta^{(k)})$. The derivations of GN ([Björck, 1996]; [Nocedal and Wright, 2006]) and LM ([Levenberg, 1944]; [Marquardt, 1963]; [Björck, 1996]; [Nocedal and Wright, 2006]) algorithms are based in equation (7).

2.2 Exponential fitting model

A common application of nonlinear least squares is the fitting of an exponential model of the form:

$$y_i = \beta_0 e^{\beta_1 x_i} + \epsilon_i, \quad (8)$$

where β_0 and β_1 are the parameters to be estimated and ϵ_i are the errors which are assumed to be i.i.d. normal with constant variance. Given a set of data points (x_i, y_i) , $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, with $m > 2$, due to the nature of the problem, the residuals can be defined by:

$$r_i = \beta_0 e^{\beta_1 x_i} - y_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (9)$$

From (9) we can obtain the Jacobian matrix of the residual function, J , whose entries are defined by the first-order derivatives of the residuals with respect to the parameters:

$$J(\beta) \equiv J = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial r_1}{\partial \beta_0} & \frac{\partial r_1}{\partial \beta_1} \\ \frac{\partial r_2}{\partial \beta_0} & \frac{\partial r_2}{\partial \beta_1} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial r_m}{\partial \beta_0} & \frac{\partial r_m}{\partial \beta_1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\beta_1 x_1} & \beta_0 x_1 e^{\beta_1 x_1} \\ e^{\beta_1 x_2} & \beta_0 x_2 e^{\beta_1 x_2} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ e^{\beta_1 x_m} & \beta_0 x_m e^{\beta_1 x_m} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

Attending that the objective function $f(\beta)$ is a continuous function that depends on parameters β_0 and β_1 , the estimates for these parameters should satisfy the following conditions when the objective function reaches its minimum:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla f(\beta) = 0 &\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \beta_0} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial f}{\partial \beta_1} = 0 \end{cases} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^m (\beta_0 e^{\beta_1 x_i} - y_i) e^{\beta_1 x_i} = 0, \\ \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_0 x_i (\beta_0 e^{\beta_1 x_i} - y_i) e^{\beta_1 x_i} = 0. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Since we cannot solve the system (11) to obtain analytical expressions for β_0 and β_1 , we have to apply numerical optimization algorithms to find a numerical approximation to the solution of this problem. When the convergence conditions are verified, these algorithms generate a sequence that converges to the solution of (11). Among the most common optimization algorithms applied to solve this problem we find the steepest descent method, GN method and LM method.

In the steepest descent method, the objective function is iteratively minimized by updating the estimates of the parameters in the direction opposite to the gradient of the objective function, that is,

$$\beta^{(k+1)} = \beta^{(k)} - \lambda_k \nabla f^{(k)}, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, \quad (12)$$

where $\lambda_k > 0$ is the step factor and $\nabla f^{(k)}$ is the gradient of the objective function f evaluated at $\beta^{(k)}$.

The GN method consists of a modification of Newton's method for minimizing the sum of squared residuals. One of the main advantages of using the GN method is that the second derivatives of the objective function, which can be challenging to compute, are not required, since the Hessian matrix of the objective function in (5) is approximated by $J^T J$. Applying this strategy, the iteration is given by:

$$\beta^{(k+1)} = \beta^{(k)} + p_k \quad (13)$$

where p_k is the solution of the system of linear equations

$$J_k^T J_k p_k = -J_k^T r^{(k)}, \quad (14)$$

where J_k and $r^{(k)}$ are the Jacobian matrix of the residual function and the residual function evaluated in $\beta^{(k)}$, respectively, and $\beta^{(k)} = (\beta_0^{(k)}, \beta_1^{(k)})$ is the numerical approximation for the estimates.

The LM method combines the steepest descent method with the GN method and is widely applied in many nonlinear minimization problems. This algorithm behaves like a steepest descent method and increases the step factor when the estimates fall far from their true values. When the objective function is reduced, the step factor is decreased and the method behaves like the GN method. Therefore, the LM method modifies the GN update rule by introducing a damping parameter λ_k :

$$(J_k^T J_k + \lambda_k I) p_k = -J_k^T r^{(k)}, \quad (15)$$

where p_k is the update step and I is the identity matrix. The damping parameter λ_k controls the transition between GN (for small λ_k) and gradient descent (for large λ_k). It is dynamically adjusted to ensure adequate descent and improve convergence stability.

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section we will see how to apply the methods, GN and LM, to solve nonlinear regression problems, more precisely, exponential regression problems. When a multiplicative change characterizes the relationship between the explanatory and response variables, it means that we will have exponential growth or exponential decay, and the best model to fit the data is the exponential model.

One of the goals of the least squares problems is to find the best model function ϕ for the observations (x_i, y_i) , $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Therefore, residuals will represent the difference between the values observed for the dependent variable and the correspondent predicted values, $\hat{y}_i = \phi(\hat{\beta}, x_i)$,

$$r_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (16)$$

where $\hat{\beta} = (\hat{\beta}_0, \hat{\beta}_1, \dots, \hat{\beta}_n)$, $n < m$, are the estimates of the parameters. Estimates for the parameters of the mathematical model are achieved by minimizing the sum of squares residuals (SSR), defined in (3), which is a special case of an unconstrained optimization problem that requires the use of specific algorithms, such as GN or LM. Since both algorithms are iterative, we need to define a stopping criterion to end the iterative process. Usually two stopping conditions are combined, one for the maximum number of iterations to be performed and another related to the convergence of the sequence generated by the method being used. A widely used stopping criterion for iterative optimization methods is based on the gradient norm of the objective function, $\|\nabla f(\beta)\| \equiv \|\nabla f\|$. Attending to the result presented in (4), the iteration process ends when the Euclidean norm of the gradient of the objective function falls below a predefined tolerance δ , ensuring that the solution is sufficiently accurate,

$$\|J^T r\| < \delta. \quad (17)$$

This criterion ensures that the optimization process stops when the residuals cannot be significantly reduced, indicating convergence to a local minimum.

The example that follows uses data observed for milk demand (price and sales) and it will be solved using the code implemented for GN and LM methods, as well as with the `nls()` function available in software [R Core Team, 2025].

3.1 Milk demand

In this example, we use a dataset that describes the milk demand¹. This dataset was obtained in a "stated preference" study, which is intended to measure someone's willingness to pay for a good or service. This study is based on the idea of giving the participants a hypothetical grocery budget, such as a menu of goods with their respective prices, and then asking them to allocate their budget as they wish. By manipulating menu prices, it

¹Data set from <https://bookdown.org/jgscott/DSGI/>

is possible to analyze people's sensitivity to buying goods at various prices. The data collected consists of 116 observations describing the relationship between the price of milk on the menu (price) and the number of participants willing to buy milk at that price (sales). A graphical representation of this data is in figure 1. According to the graph,

Figure 1: Milk demand observations.

is evident that people are less willing to buy milk when prices are higher. The idea is to fit a model to this data, and in this case, the chosen is the exponential regression model.

Figure 2: First iterations obtained with Gauss-Newton.

k	$\beta_0^{(k)}$	$\beta_1^{(k)}$	$f(\beta^{(k)}; x, y)$	$\frac{\ \beta^{(k+1)} - \beta^{(k)}\ }{\ \beta^{(k+1)}\ }$	$\ \nabla f(\beta^{(k)}; x, y)\ $
0	50.0	-0.5	16369.504	0.689	44300.0
1	161.00382	-0.96925715	12678.118	0.209	43700.0
2	203.44808	-0.68683065	6405.2700	0.0537	61600.0
3	193.07701	-0.75318498	3709.1803	0.0397	5220.0
4	201.06064	-0.78238895	3669.1529	0.0131	144.0
5	203.73110	-0.78844924	3668.3376	0.00235	25.5
6	204.21179	-0.7895287	3668.3119	0.000406	6.62
7	204.29464	-0.78971976	3668.3111	7.13e-05	1.24
8	204.30921	-0.78975354	3668.3111	1.26e-05	0.221
9	204.31179	-0.78975951	3668.3111	2.23e-06	0.0391
10	204.31224	-0.78976057	3668.3111	—	0.00692

Table 1: Results obtained with implemented code for GN method applied to milk demand data set.

Figure 2 shows the data collected, the initial guess used to apply the GN method, and the results returned for the first and second iterations. This gives us a graphical insight into the idea of how convergence is processed when using this method.

The `nls()` function with the initial guess

$$\beta^{(0)} = (\beta_0^{(0)}, \beta_1^{(0)}) = (50, -0.5) \quad (18)$$

and setting the tolerance to 0.5×10^{-1} for the Euclidean norm of the gradient of f , the results obtained are presented in table 1.

Next, we use the `nls()` function available in **R** software to estimate the parameters of the exponential model. The output is presented below, and it corroborates the results achieved with our code.

```
Nonlinear regression model
  model: sales ~ beta0 * exp(beta1 * price)
  data: parent.frame()
  beta0    beta1
204.3118 -0.7898
residual sum-of-squares: 7337

Number of iterations to convergence: 9
Achieved convergence tolerance: 2.364e-06
```

From this output (or from table 1) we obtain the following mathematical expression of the estimated exponential model:

$$\hat{y}_{Sales_i} = 204.312e^{-0.7898Price_i}, \quad i = 1, \dots, 116. \quad (19)$$

Next, we apply LM method to solve the same problem using `gsl_nls()` function available in `gsl_nls` package in **R** software.

```

iter  1: ssr = 28871.4, par = (50.0126, -0.152326)
iter  2: ssr = 18370.6, par = (50.0304, -0.254971)
iter  3: ssr = 18232.8, par = (50.0782, -0.271097)
iter  4: ssr = 18197.9, par = (50.2052, -0.271162)
iter  5: ssr = 18095.6, par = (50.5840, -0.273709)
iter  6: ssr = 17801.4, par = (51.6954, -0.280943)
iter  7: ssr = 17020.2, par = (54.8253, -0.300889)
iter  8: ssr = 15311.5, par = (62.7797, -0.348652)
iter  9: ssr = 12704.8, par = (79.3688, -0.435222)
iter 10: ssr = 10306.8, par = (102.892, -0.52939)
iter 11: ssr = 8612.71, par = (131.630, -0.620521)
iter 12: ssr = 7690.65, par = (163.170, -0.703107)
iter 13: ssr = 7386.73, par = (187.751, -0.756493)
iter 14: ssr = 7339.82, par = (199.827, -0.780482)
iter 15: ssr = 7336.75, par = (203.403, -0.787752)
iter 16: ssr = 7336.63, par = (204.146, -0.789379)
iter 17: ssr = 7336.62, par = (204.282, -0.789692)
iter 18: ssr = 7336.62, par = (204.307, -0.789748)
iter 19: ssr = 7336.62, par = (204.311, -0.789759)
iter 20: ssr = 7336.62, par = (204.312, -0.78976)
iter 21: ssr = 7336.62, par = (204.312, -0.789761)
iter 22: ssr = 7336.62, par = (204.312, -0.789761)
iter 23: ssr = 7336.62, par = (204.312, -0.789761)
iter 24: ssr = 7336.62, par = (204.312, -0.789761)
*****
summary from method 'multifit/levenberg-marquardt'
number of iterations: 24
initial ssr: 32739
final ssr: 7336.62
ssr/dof: 64.3563
ssr achieved tolerance: -9.09495e-13
function evaluations: 78
jacobian evaluations: 0
fvv evaluations: 0

```

```
status: success
*****
Nonlinear regression model
  model: y ~ beta0 * (exp(beta1 * x))
  data: milk
  beta0    beta1
204.3123 -0.7898
residual sum-of-squares: 7337
```

Algorithm: multifit/levenberg-marquardt, (scaling: levenberg, solver: qr)

Number of iterations to convergence: 24

Achieved convergence tolerance: -9.095e-13

The results obtained show that in an initially stage the algorithm converges slowly, this is because the damping factor tends to be large to ensure convergence, i.e. the algorithm behaves like the steepest descent method. This happens because we are starting with an initial approximation that lies far from the solution of the system (11). As approximations become closer to the limit, the damping factor tends to be smaller, close to zero, and the algorithm starts to behave like GN method, converging faster to the limit. Figure 3 shows the data points, the initial guess, and the first two iterations obtained with this method.

Figure 3: First iterations obtained with Levenberg-Marquardt.

4 FINAL REMARKS

In Numerical Analysis, some algorithms were developed to find a solution to linear least squares problems. However, although linear regression models generally present good results in most practical applications, there are situations where considering a nonlinear model is more appropriate. This preliminary study relies on the knowledge acquired in Numerical Analysis, where finding a computational solution in some complex situations is possible. In this context, Numerical Optimization provides a set of algorithms that can be applied to solve nonlinear regression problems, such as the GN and LM methods, which were implemented and used in the statistical software through `nls()` and `gsl_nls()` functions. Both tools were applied to obtain estimates of parameters in exponential regression problems.

The global convergence of the LM method is ensured under mild conditions and exhibits local superlinear convergence when residuals are small. Compared to other methods such as the GN method, this method provides a more stable and computationally efficient framework for solving linear least-squares problems, particularly in the cases of overdetermined systems or high-dimensional parameter spaces.

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